

Designing an Architecture for machine-actionable Research Data Management Planning in an institutional Context

Master Thesis Proposal

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1 Introduction

Today's scientific research is data-intensive and requires activities ranging from data capture, curation and analysis to long-term preservation [7]. In order to make data-intensive scientific results reproducible, the underlying data needs to be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). Therefore the FAIR principles [20], which provide measurable guidelines for good data management, were established. Research data management following the FAIR principles enables not only the validation and verification of scientific results but also the discovery of new knowledge based on reused data.

To maximize the effectiveness of research funding and foster good research practice, grant-giving organizations like the European Commission or the U.S. National Science Foundation (NSF) require researchers to write and maintain Data Management Plans (DMP) accompanying their research projects. Research projects funded by the EU Horizon 2020 programme require a DMP which describes how research data is being made FAIR [2]. Among other things a DMP outlines what kind of research data will be created, its expected volume, how it will be documented, which kind of metadata standards are used, how the data is being stored and backed-up during the project, how it will be shared, which license applies, how it will be published and preserved beyond the funding [4].

2 Problem Statement

DMPs to date are free-form text created with text processors or online tools such as DMPonline¹ or DMPTool² and exported as pdf or another non-machine-actionable file format. Aforementioned tools present open questions to the researcher covering DMP themes and provide funder specific templates for additional guidance. Often the guidance is perceived as too complicated, technical, vague or generic and researchers have problems answering the questions [6]. The quality of the DMP therefore depends heavily on the expertise of the authors. Unknowing researchers are unaware of the technical capabilities of appropriate research tools, storage, metadata standards, licenses or repositories, and choose poor data management options.

A major drawback stems from the static nature of a DMP, the information contained therein is not favorable to machine processing. The DMP degrades to human-readable only narrative and stays behind its full potential of being a satisfying, integral part of research to improve data management practice among researchers. Researchers perceive it as an administrative burden with limited use to write and maintain DMPs. The experience of writing a DMP is a static one, there do not exist any means of automation such as pre-populating a DMP with data contained in related information systems, analyzing file samples to guide the further process, selecting a license based on funder policies or calculating a data management cost estimation. On the other side, consumers of the DMP such as funders have to manually review them to check for policy compliance. Other stakeholders involved in the research process like repository operators are not involved in data management planning to assist with data curation to enable a seamless transfer to their repositories at the end of a research project. ICT operators providing computing resources and storage are excluded from data management planning and are not informed about upcoming demands to plan their resources efficiently.

3 Expected Result (Aim and Scope)

Several initiatives (cf. section 5) have identified the limitations of current DMPs and suggest to deploy DMPs in a machine-actionable data format to enable information flow across research systems and an automation of workflows. Potential use cases [18], [19] and requirements [10] for machine-actionable DMPs (maDMPs) and support systems were identified by the community.

The aim of this work is to pick up the community ideas around maDMPs, concretize and develop them further in order to show their feasibility in an institutional context such as a research institution or university. This involves the

¹ <https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk>

² <https://dmptool.org>

- identification of relevant stakeholders at an institution and related organizations (e.g. funder) with their potential benefits of a machine-actionable data management planning infrastructure.
- development and description of workflows / business processes for machine-actionable data management planning.
- the system architecture description on an enterprise level that could serve as a basis for establishing a reference architecture for maDMPs at institutions.
- development of a demonstrator that shows selected features of the described architecture.

The architecture design shall describe how machine-actionable data management planning could be embedded into an institutional research data management infrastructure. This involves the integration of services relevant for data management at the institution like a Current Research Information System (CRIS), ICT services and institutional archives, but also external information systems and services.

Existing data management planning tools have a strong focus on educating researchers in good data management practice and guiding them through the process of data management planning by asking open questions and providing hints based on funder policies or guidelines established by experts, such as the Digital Curation Center. In contrast to that, the scope of this work is not on open questions, guidance and completeness of themes covered by DMPs, but on establishing semi-automatic workflows for data management planning by means of system integration and automation. For that purpose services that create structured machine-actionable information, that could be fed into a DMP and services that can consume this information and act upon it are required. In this work the possibilities of establishing a support system for machine-actionable DMPs at an institution shall be explored. Therefore the following research questions are formulated and shall be addressed in this work.

- RQ1. What is the architecture supporting machine-actionable data management planning at a research institution?
- (a) To which degree is the architecture institution-specific?
 - (b) Which parts of the architecture could be deployed at a bigger scale?
- RQ2. Which tasks of data management planning can be supported with system integration and automation?
- RQ3. To which extent can we integrate RDM services offered at the institution with data management planning?
- RQ4. To which extent can we support the communication between stakeholders of research data management?
- RQ5. To which extent can we design services that act on behalf of stakeholders involved in research data management?

4 Method

In order to pursue the aforementioned aim of the work (cf. section 3) and be able to answer the associated research questions, the following steps involving the stated methods will be carried out.

Fig. 1. Overview of the research method to achieve the expected result.

1. **Concepts:** Study community-driven ideas and outcomes towards maDMPs and best practices on research data management. Identify useful services and tools associated with the maDMP vision. Develop and describe use cases and workflows for machine-actionable data management planning in an institutional context. Use standard modeling languages such as UML and BPMN.
2. **Design:** Design and describe the architecture for realizing the defined workflows at a research institution. Use standard system engineering techniques such as Enterprise Architecture (EA) modeling and a standard description format, e.g. Rational Unified Process (RUP) Software Architecture Document³ (SAD). Use a stakeholder viewpoint-oriented architecture description such as the 4+1 architectural view model by Kruchten [9]. Use suitable architecture modeling languages such as ArchiMate and UML to create concurrent views of the EA.
3. **Implementation & Evaluation:** Develop a demonstrator that shows selected features of the described architecture. Choose suitable technologies and describe selected implementation details of interest. Use the existing TU Wien RDM infrastructure (e.g. information systems, ICT services) to evaluate the demonstrator in an institutional context. Evaluate the demonstrator and the underlying architecture by comparing it against expected properties and criteria defined during conceptualization.
4. **Future Work:** Identify and discuss shortcomings, limitations and gaps and outline future work to overcome them.

³ http://sce.uhcl.edu/helm/RationalUnifiedProcess/webtmpl/templates/a_and_d/rup_sad.htm

An overview of the research method showing the involved steps is depicted in Figure 1.

5 State-of-the-Art (Related Work)

DMPs are written in free-form text with the aid of checklists [4], templates or tools who guide through the planning process. The most prominent online tools for creating a DMP are DMPonline⁴ and DMPTool⁵. Its developers, the California Digital Library UC3 and the Digital Curation Center in Edinburgh, joined together and use the same codebase under the DMPRoadmap⁶ project [8]. These tools guide the researchers through a set of open questions covering the themes of a DMP and provide templates for funder-specific guidance based on the selected RDM policy. In addition, these tools allow to collaboratively create DMPs, share and export them to various formats such as pdf, html or docx. DMPRoadmap is an open source project and can be adopted and branded by other institutions, e.g. DMPTuuli⁷ from Finland or DMP OPIDoR⁸ from France. In 2017 the California Digital Library received funding from the NSF to develop DMPRoadmap with national and international collaborators towards machine-actionability [13].

There are many other tools for creating DMPs on the market, a good overview of available platforms is given by Jones et al. [8]. The Data Stewardship Wizard⁹ is based on a knowledge model represented by a decision tree that guides the researcher through a set of questions based on the previous answers. RDMOrganiser¹⁰ (RDMO) offers similar functionalities like DMPonline and DMPTool but is intended to be deployed on RDM infrastructures of institutions within Germany, in contrast to hosting a central national or international instance. The University of Queensland Research Data Manager¹¹ (UQRDM) is a researcher-centric and user friendly tool that follows an integrated approach and allows to actively manage data storage and access control. Data storage is automatically provisioned from the cloud computing platform QRIScloud¹² after creating a record in UQRDM. In this context, the term Data Management Record (DMR) instead of DMP is used to emphasize that a DMR remains linked to the research data throughout the lifecycle of the project and relevant metadata is captured by the system, reducing the administrative burden on researchers [17]. The Research Data Box¹³ (ReDBox), also from Australia, is a research data

⁴ <https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk>

⁵ <https://dmptool.org>

⁶ <https://github.com/DMPRoadmap/roadmap>

⁷ <https://www.dmptuuli.fi/>

⁸ <https://dmp.opidor.fr/>

⁹ <https://dsw.fairdata.solutions>

¹⁰ <https://rdmorganiser.github.io/en/>

¹¹ <https://research.uq.edu.au/project/research-data-manager-uqrdm>

¹² <https://www.qriscloud.org.au/>

¹³ <https://www.redboxresearchdata.com.au/>

management platform that connects research activities with research data, eResearch infrastructure and services for processing, storing and managing research data [1]. ReDBox offers a DMP tool that integrates a provisioner service which allows researchers to create a workspace for self-provisioning and managing cloud services such as GitLab code repository or LabArchive electronic lab notebook.

Currently there is a great interest in enhancing DMPs towards machine-actionability by various groups and organizations. The Research Data Alliance (RDA) hosts interest and working groups in this area. The RDA Active DMPs interest group [14] maintains a wiki to collect community ideas and relevant material. RDA DMP Common Standards working group is engaged in establishing a common information model and specifying access mechanisms for machine-actionable DMPs to allow system interoperability [15]. A related RDA working group called Exposing DMPs is concerned with collecting stakeholder use cases for publishing DMPs and deriving a reference model from them [16]. The FORCE11 FAIR DMP group works on principles and best practices for good data management and machine-readability to make research data FAIR [5]. The Australian National Data Service (ANDS) facilitates a DMPs interest group to provide a forum for discussions on international developments and the future of DMPs [3].

Several papers on machine-actionable DMPs have been published. The future of next-generation DMPs is discussed by Simms and Jones [18]. The white paper on maDMPs by Simms et al. [19] reports IDCC17 workshop outcomes and maDMP use cases identified by experts. Miksa et al. [12] suggest ten simple rules for machine-actionable DMPs. Jones et al. [8] give an overview on the landscape of current developments in the area of active DMPs. Requirements for maDMPs are defined by Miksa et al. [10]. Miksa et al. present a mapping of tools, which can provide automated information, to sections of a DMP [11]. The survey report on the Horizon 2020 template for DMPs by Jones et al. [6] gives suggestions on improvements of DMP tools.

6 Relation to the Software Engineering & Internet Computing Curriculum

The topics and work involved in this master thesis touch the Software Engineering & Internet Computing curriculum in many ways. DMPs are subject of digital preservation and stewardship covered in the Advanced Security module. The design and development of an enterprise architecture includes software engineering tasks such as requirements engineering and knowledge of distributed systems and networking, which are addressed in the respective modules. The development of a demonstrator requires the engineering of web applications including the selection of suitable technologies as covered by the Internet Computing and Distributed Systems Technologies module. The following not exhaustive list shows modules and associated courses of the curriculum that are related to the thesis.

- Advanced Security
 - 3.0/2.0 VO Digital Preservation
 - 3.0/2.0 UE Digital Preservation
- Software Engineering
 - 3.0/2.0 VU Requirements Engineering and Specification
- Distributed Systems and Networking
 - 3.0/2.0 VU Software Architecture
 - 3.0/2.0 VU Distributed Systems Engineering
 - 3.0/2.0 VU Web Application Engineering and Content Management
- Internet Computing and Distributed Systems Technologies
 - 6.0/4.0 VU Distributed Systems Technologies
 - 3.0/2.0 VU Advanced Internet Computing

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